

Speculation on NonZero Rest Mass Momentum as Source of Quantum Action-Reaction

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In a previous note (1) we argued that two flux/flow equations $d/dx \text{ partial } A(x,t)=p$ ((1a)) and $ddt \text{ partial } A(x,t) = -E$ ((1b)) lead to the Lorentz invariant solution $A(x,t)= -Et+px$. These have two stationary solutions ($dA=0$), namely $dE/dv= dp/dv$ with $x/t=v$ and $p=E(v)v$ (rest mass nonzero) and $dx/dt = E/p$ (rest mass i.e. a classical wave). The first solution leads to relativistic/nonrelativistic quantum mechanics if ((1a)) and ((1b)) are written as eigenvalue equations. The second represents classical waves and their eigenfunction equation is the classical wave equation $d/dt d/dt \cos(A) = 1/vv d/dx docs(A)/dx$.

A periodic solution, we argue, implies action-reaction suggesting force or tension in the system. This seems to be the case for a classical wave on a string with fixed ends or for a sound wave in a gas with pressure. Light treated as a classical wave, however, is more complicated because there is no medium with tension, but rather one has periodically varying electric and magnetic fields. An electric field, however, is considered a force field and so there is an analogy with a periodically changing pressure. A classical wave requires a real periodic solution.

A quantum mechanical free particle solution (nonzero rest mass) does not require a real periodic solution because there is no medium or obvious real entity changing periodically, but one may establish a complex solution using eigenvalue equations: $id/dt \text{ partial } \exp(iA) = E \exp(iA)$ and $-id/dx \text{ partial } \exp(iA) = p \exp(iA)$. At first a complex solution seems unphysical, but one may note that for a fixed t (for example), $\exp(ipx)$ is 1 at $x=0$ and again at $pL=2\pi$. Thus there is a special length in the problem which yields the classical mechanical result $d/dx \text{ partial } A = p$ namely the wavelength $2\pi/p$. In other words the quantum solution describes the classical solution at each $x= n \cdot \text{wavelength}$. Within each wavelength region one has an $\exp(ipx)$ solution which consists of two out of phase periodic functions such that the modulus is 1.

We try to argue that like in a classical wave there should be some impedance to a disturbance (like tension of a string or pressure of a gas). This impedance, however, is not represented by one physical entity (e.g. pressure in a sound wave) as one has a complex solution.

A complex solution $\exp(ipx)$ is not alarming because light treated as a classical wave has two perpendicular entities, namely the electric and magnetic fields, that are both periodic. One may write a classical wave equation for each, but one may write a combined quantum-like wave equation for a photon: $i d/dt \text{ partial } W_i + e_{ijk} (-id/dx_j) W_k = 0$ (where e_{ijk} is the Levi-Civita symbol) which has a vector wavefunction $W_i = \text{Electric field } (i)(x,t) + i \text{Magnetic field } (i)(x,t)$.

The only impedance in the zero rest mass problem seems to be the rest mass (inertia) which resists motion. To be more general, it seems that momentum overall should be an impedance to motion. The entire momentum ($E(v)v$) is associated with an impact and a change in the momentum of a quantum particle (with rest mass) may be resisted by the entire momentum. In classical physics constant velocity motion seems to be a simple translation from one x point to another. The $\exp(ipx)$ solution to ((1a)) and ((1b)) shows that this interpretation only holds for $n \cdot \text{wavelength}$ points. Within each wavelength region out of phase two dimensional periodic

motion occurs which suggests a kind of action-reaction. This behaviour occurs for various objects such as an electron, nucleon, nucleus, atom or even fairly large molecules etc. It has been argued that this quantum motion may apply for even objects in the macroscopic world e.g. mirrors. Impedance for nonzero rest mass quantum objects is velocity dependent as one may have many different velocities associated with a nonzero rest mass momentum while classical waves have one velocity (for a given tension scenario). E.g. light always has a velocity of c because it has only one tension scenario i.e. electric and magnetic fields. Changing wavelengths and frequencies are linked to changing energy and momentum, but not velocity.

We try to investigate some of these ideas.

Action-Reaction

Classical wave behaviour was well known before quantum mechanics, with waves on a string, sound and classical em light waves being examples. These follow: $\text{velocity} = \text{constant} = E/p$. Waves on a string and sound waves require a medium with tension (tension in the string or pressure in a gas). A light wave requires a changing electric and magnetic field, but an electric field is proportional to a force (although there is no charge in the problem). Thus in all cases there is an existing "force field" so to speak which may be made to change periodically (action reaction) giving rise to the notion of a classical wave. The speed of this wave is constant as it is a result of an existing tension or force field.

Quantum mechanical solutions of the Schrodinger equation, Klein-Gordon or Dirac equations etc for free particles exhibit wave-like forms $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$, but are complex (unlike a classical wave), have the relation $p=E(v)/v$ (unlike a classical wave) and do not seem to have any obvious tension. Thus quantum mechanics is said to represent a probability wave. Nevertheless the periodic nature of the solution seems to imply action-reaction.

Secondly, quantum mechanical wave type objects (linked to particles with rest mass) may have different velocities unlike a classical wave (or even photon/phonon). This suggests an impedance which is not due to some fixed force or tension field (e.g. pressure, string tension, an existing electric field etc). It seems that for the quantum nonzero rest mass case the impedance is linked to something that is velocity dependent and has two dimensions. It is known that rest mass provides impedance and it seems that this may be generalized to overall momentum which depends on velocity. In other words the quantum probability wave may be a momentum wave although it somehow has to depend on two dimensions (associated with forward and backward motion). This is similar to a photon which has a wavelength of electric field + i magnetic field. The momentum density is created by electric field x magnetic and each change periodically.

Flow/flux Equations

In previous notes (1) we argue that classical Lagrangian mechanics, free particle quantum mechanics and classical waves all follow from two flux/flow equations:

$$d/dx \text{ partial } A(x,t) = p \quad ((1a)) \quad d/dt \text{ partial } A(x,t) = -E \quad ((1b)) \quad \text{with } A(x,t) = -Et+px$$

$-Et+px$ is a Lorentz invariant. As argued in (1) there are two approaches to maintaining $A(x,t)$ constant. For a classical wave: $dA=0 = -Edt+pd x$ from which: $v=\text{constant}=E/p$. Alternatively $dE/dv (-t') + dp/dv (x') = 0$ with $x'/t'=v$ ((1)). This is linked to $p=Ev$ for a particle with rest mass and one may obtain the form of special relativity from ((2)).

The flux/flow equations may be generalized. For a classical wave one may consider an eigenfunction equation for a real periodic function i.e. the classical wave equation:

$$d/dt d/dt \cos(-Et+px) = 1/vv \quad d/dx d/dx \cos(-Et+px) \quad ((3))$$

This is a second order equation, but the physical periodic behaviour follows from tension in the system such as tension in a string or pressure in a gas.

A quantum periodic solution is different. It follows from:

$$id/dt \exp(-iEt+ipx) = E \exp(-iEt+ipx) \quad ((4a)) \quad \text{and} \quad -id/dx \exp(-iEt+ipx) = p \exp(-iEt+ipx) \quad ((4b))$$

At first this result is unusual in that it contains a complex solution $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$. One may note, however, that for a fixed t , $\exp(ipx) = 1$ for $x = 2\pi n/p$ ($n=0,1,2,\dots$). Thus at intervals of $pL=2\pi$, one obtains the classical solution ((1a)) and ((1b)). This may be interpreted as saying that "unusual periodic" behaviour occurs within each L region but at each nL one has the classical solution.

Given that the quantum free particle solution and the classical wave follow from the same flux equations ((1a)) and ((1b)) we argue that the physical action-reaction mechanism (tension, gas pressure) causing the classical wave should have a physical analogue for the free particle nonzero rest mass quantum solution. Furthermore small values of $\cos(px)$ from $\exp(ipx)$ imply a low probability for mass-energy to be at these x values.

Two Dimensions and $\exp(ipx)$

In a probabilistic description probability cannot disappear from a point x without appearing at another point. There is one particle and there needs to be conservation of probability. Thus $\exp(ipx) * \exp(-ipx) = 1$ showing no effects of the special wavelength units at the overall density level. In other words there is no perceived local variation in spatial density.

A free particle trapped in a box with infinite potential walls, however, is localized and one may see regions with high spatial density and regions with low. (The wavefunction in this localized case, however, is a superposition of all $\exp(ipx)$ which exist in all of space and not just the localized region.) A two slit interference pattern with electrons shows a similar pattern.

Thus the issue of the two dimensions associated with $\exp(ipx)$ seem to be linked to localization. For a free particle with rest mass moving in one direction the components $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ exist, but for all bound problems including a particle in a box with infinite potential walls, the second dimension disappears due to interference. With localization probability may disappear from certain spatial regions, but it must be added to other regions so that overall it is conserved. Thus the two dimensions of probability seem to be linked to momentum as a particle

moving to the right has $\cos(px)$ and $i\sin(px)$ while one moving to the left has $\cos(px)$ and $-i\sin(px)$. The second dimension is somehow linked to momentum direction.

Link with Force

We have argued that an unusual periodic nonclassical pattern may occur within each wavelength region due to momentum which acts as an impedance. This unusual periodic pattern, however, may also be seen for a potential written as:

$$V(x) = \sum_k V_k \exp(ikx) \quad ((5))$$

If one assumes that $\exp(ikx)$ delivers a change in momentum impulse of k , then:

$$\exp(ipx)\exp(ikx) = \exp(i(p+k)x) \quad ((6))$$

((6)) implies that an impulse of k may occur at any x , but one may note that $\exp(ikx)$ also exhibits a wavelength. Thus the idea of spatial resolution due to a wavelength does not only apply to a free particle moving at constant velocity, but also to “components” of a potential. $V(x)$ is only an average so each x is resolved as an average result. We argue that a free particle with constant velocity acts as a piece of potential itself as it may strike an object and deliver an impulse. Thus the $\exp(ipx)$ behaviour of the free particle is similar to that of the potential $\exp(ikx)$.

Conclusion

In conclusion, although we note that the above is speculative, we also argue that if both classical waves and free particle (nonzero rest mass) quantum mechanics follow from the same flux equations ((1a)) and ((1b)) and if periodic motion in a classical wave is due to physical tension (action-reaction) e.g. tension in string or pressure in a gas, then similar physical tension should exist for a quantum particle with rest mass. The only explicit impedance to a disturbance of the particle seems to be momentum. Inertia which is linked to a rest mass already shows impedance and this is part of the overall momentum.

For $-i\hbar/dx \exp(ipx) = p \exp(ipx)$ there exists a classical mechanical solution at every $x = 2\pi \cdot 3.14 \cdot n/p$ where $n=0,1,2,\dots$. Within each wavelength region there seems to be two dimensional periodic motion occurring due to the momentum we argue. The need for two dimensions is due to discerning the direction of momentum flow. In other words, for a particle moving in one direction probability should be conserved at each x , so $\exp(ipx)$ has a modulus of 1, but a particle in a box with an infinite potential shows the distinct high-low probability regions as there is now localization. Probability lost at one point may show up at another to yield global conservation i.e. $\int dx W^*(x)W(x) = 1$ where $W(x)$ is the wavefunction. It may be noted that a particle in a box with an infinite potential is really a superposition of all $\exp(ikx)$ which exist in all space, but the result mimics the real part of a free particle wavefunction with wave within the box such that the wavefunction is zero at the walls of the box. Furthermore, all bound states

have a real wavefunction i.e. only one dimension of the various $\exp(ipx)$'s is manifest showing clearly a periodic spatial density $W(x)W(x)$.

We further note that a potential $V(x)=\text{Sum over } k V_k \exp(ikx)$ has a similar form and that a free quantum particle may be thought of as supplying impulse hits of momentum just as $\exp(ikx)$ from the potential delivers momentum hits of k .

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Free Particle Stationary Action Solutions Linked to Zero/Nonzero Rest Mass Waves And Special Relativity (preprint, zenodo, 2022).